

Automatic Analysis of Magnetogram Sequences for Solar Flares Forecasting

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ABSTRACT

Solar flares are releases of electromagnetic energy that occur on the Sun's surface and can reach the Earth's atmosphere in a few hours or minutes. Depending on the flares intensity, such as M- or X-class flares, they can have a big impact on some activities and technologies, particularly satellite, telecommunications, and electrical power systems. Therefore, predicting the occurrence of solar flares helps mitigate their effects on Earth. Solar flares occur in active solar regions. These regions with magnetic fields, known as sunspots, can be precursors to solar flares. Observing the evolution of active regions through a set of solar images, such as magnetograms, is possible. A magnetogram is an image of the intensity and location of magnetic fields in the solar magnetosphere. The emergence process of solar flares generally lasts from 72h to 96h. Thus, more recent works started to combine image-based and time series Deep Learning models to consider the evolution of active regions in the Sun. Therefore, we propose an automatic solar flare forecasting system based on 3D Convolutional Neural Networks, capable of extracting learning parameters in the temporal spectrum of an image sequence, for forecasting an M or X classes solar flare in the next 48h. In preliminary tests, the fine-tuned ResNet 2D+1 model reached compatible results (F1 = 0.56, HSS = 0.55, TSS = 0.48) according to the state-of-the-art models optimized for the F1 metric.

Keywords: Solar Flares, Deep Learning, Magnetogram Sequences, Forecasting.

INTRODUCTION

Solar flares are intense and temporary energy releases caused by sudden changes in the magnetic field of the Sun's surface. They usually occur when magnetic regions of different polarities in the solar disk approach and create magnetic arcs, becoming an Active Region (AR). The energy released by solar flares can propagate into space through the solar wind, affecting Earth's atmosphere in a few hours or minutes. Therefore, solar flares are considered one of the most significant events on the Sun [1].

The ARs are better known as sunspots, which can be precursors of solar flares. We can observe sunspots using solar magnetograms, that is, images taken by an instrument that can detect the strength and location of magnetic fields on the Sun. In a magnetogram, the darker areas are regions of south magnetic polarity (facing inwards or moving towards the center of the Sun), the lighter regions indicate north polarity (facing outwards, moving towards us), and the neutral areas indicate there is no magnetic field.

The effects of solar flares can affect the atmosphere and the space near Earth. Some of its effects include the shutdown or failure of aerospace systems (such as the recent event that caused the loss of 40 newly launched Starlink satellites on February 4th, 2022¹, communication, navigation, power generation, also oil and gas pipelines [1]. The occurrence and severity of many of these effects depend on the intensity of solar flares, classified according to the release of electromagnetic radiation between classes A, B, C, M, and X. Each class has its peak x-ray flux ten times larger than its predecessor. Furthermore, each class varies on a linear scale from 1 to 9, representing the intensity of the flare [1].

In the past decade, researchers have already obtained good results in machine learning models, which receive numerical parameters extracted from magnetograms as input, to forecast solar flares [2,1]. In the last five years, the authors started using Deep Learning techniques to forecast directly on the images obtained from the magnetograms [3,4]. Deep Learning techniques are part of machine learning methods based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have been one of the most widely used Deep Learning techniques in image recognition since the 1980s.

CNNs are feedforward ANNs, as the information flow occurs in a single direction, from inputs to outputs, and can have many variations. However, in general, they consist of convolutional and pooling layers grouped into modules [5]. One or more fully connected layers follow these modules, which are usually stacked on top of each other, creating a deep model. Due to the increase in computational power and the amount of training data, in recent years, CNNs have achieved superhuman performance in some complex visual tasks, such as problems related to image classification, object detection in images, and segmentation of images [5].

As the emergence process of solar flares generally lasts from 72h to 96h (3 to 5 days) [6], more recent work has started to combine image-based Deep Learning models with models that also consider time-series sequences, combining CNNs with Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) [7,8].

¹ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-60317806>

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we present the methodology proposed for this work detailing the dataset used, the creation of AR image sequences, the forecasting models and their implementation, and the most common performance evaluation metrics for solar flare forecasting.

Dataset

The dataset² used in this work comprises 59384 samples of high-quality magnetograms captured by the HMI/SDO from May 4, 2010, to December 30, 2015 (from the initial to the peak period of solar cycle 24). The HMI instrument provides these data (`hmi.sharp_720s`), making new samples available every 12 minutes. However, the samples from this dataset were collected every 96 minutes [3].

It is the same dataset used in Tang's et al work [7]. Each sample has an associated magnetogram, a ready-made snippet of an AR, ten magnetic parameters from SHARP, and a label. The positive label (1) indicates that the specific AR generated a solar flare of class $\geq M$ in the next 48h from the observation. The negative label (0) indicates that the AR did not generate an $\geq M$ explosion in the next 48h. This is a highly unbalanced dataset, as it presents only about 5% (2837) of class-positive samples and about 95% (56869) of class-negative samples. We only used the image of the associated magnetogram and its label, discarding the magnetic numeric parameters.

As in Tang et al. [7], we first discard samples with missing data and then perform the division of the sets. We use the first 40 000 samples ($\approx 67\%$) for training; for validation, we considered 10 000 samples, between the sample 40 001 and 50 000 ($\approx 16.8\%$); for the test, we considered the remaining 9384 samples ($\approx 16.2\%$), which corresponds to the period until the end of 2015.

Active Regions Image Sequences

We considered the sliding window method for each instant to assemble AR images sequences. This strategy is similar to the method applied by Tang et al. [7] to the ARs numerical parameters. The differential of our work was to consider ARs magnetograms images sequences, creating a kind of evolution video for each AR. We describe the sliding window method in Equation 1.

$$SeqT = [T - \Delta t, \dots, T - 2, T - 1, T] \quad (1)$$

where T is the current time; Δt is the window size; and $SeqT$ is a time series that starts with $T - \Delta t$, has size Δt and ends at the current instant of time T . As discussed in Yu et al. [6], the emergence process of solar flares generally lasts from 72h to 96h. Considering a forecast horizon for the next 48h (2 days), it would be reasonable to consider a sliding window with data from the current instant T up to 72h (3 days) earlier. As the data set used has a cadence of 96 minutes (1h36), the maximum size of Δt would be 45 instants.

² Available at [\url{https://tianchi-competition.oss-cn-hangzhou.aliyuncs.com/531804/dataset_ss2sf.zip}](https://tianchi-competition.oss-cn-hangzhou.aliyuncs.com/531804/dataset_ss2sf.zip)

At the beginning of AR monitoring, there is not enough data to completely compose the sliding window, so Yu et al. [6] suggest creating an artificial sequence repeating the available samples. This strategy was adopted throughout the dataset for a closer evaluation of the operational scenario, considering the proportional repetition of the available observations.

Forecasting models with 3D Convolutions

We implement models to forecast solar flares based on image sequences using CNNs with the concept of 3D convolutions, like ResNet 3D, ResNet MC (*Mixed Convolution*) and ResNet (2+1)D [9], as illustrated in Figure 1 below. CNNs with 3D convolutions can learn spatio-temporal correlations in image sequences or videos.

In Figure 1, the abbreviation “fc” represents the fully connected layer, and we omitted the residual connections for ease of interpretation. In turn, ResNet (2+1)D features are factored into convolutional filters into separate spatial and temporal components. This produced accuracy gains over ResNet 3D and ResNet MC of 2% to 5% [9]. For convenience, we will refer to the set of these three models as RES3D.

Figure 1. CNNs that apply 3D convolutions. Adapted from Tran et al. [9].

In addition to the forecasting models based on image sequences, we evaluated the models AlexNet [10] and ResNet18 [11] to provide a basis for comparison. These base models do the forecasting with single images without considering the sequence of images.

Models general configuration and implementation

We used PyTorch³ framework to load the torchvision models AlexNet and ResNet18 (CNNs2D) with the Imagenet dataset [12] weights and ResNet 3D, ResNet MC and ResNet 2D+1 (RES3D) with the Kinetics-400 dataset [13] weights. After that, we changed the fc layer of all models to two output units and performed a fine-tuning training (also known as transfer learning) for 10 epochs with batches of 10 samples in a PyTorch Lightning⁴ module. We also used the Cross Entropy Loss function and Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) for all models. We set initial learning rate (LR) to 0.1 for CNNs2D and to 0.001 for the RES3D, with decay multiplied by 0.1 every three epochs for all models. The inputs were normalized in the range of 0 to 1 for all models and resized to 256x256 pixels for CNNs2D and 112x112 pixels for RES3D. We also used Neptune⁵ to track the experiments.

Metrics to performance evaluation

To evaluate the performance, we used metrics that consider correctly predicted positive samples (True Positives - TP); correctly predicted negative samples (True Negatives - TN); incorrectly predicted positive samples (False Positives - FP); and incorrectly predicted negative samples (False Negatives - FN). These metrics are Accuracy (ACC), Probability of Detection (POD), Precision (PRE), False-Alarm Ratio (FAR), Critical Success Index (CSI), F1 Score (F1), Hiedke Skill Score (HSS), and True Skill Statistic (TSS) as follows:

$$\bullet \text{ ACC} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{TN} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ POD} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ PRE} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ FAR} = \frac{\text{FP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ CSI} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ F1} = \frac{2 \times \text{PRE} \times \text{POD}}{\text{PRE} + \text{POD}}$$

$$\bullet \text{ HSS} = \frac{2 \times (\text{TP} \times \text{TN} - \text{FP} \times \text{FN})}{(\text{TP} + \text{FN}) \times (\text{FN} + \text{TN}) + (\text{TP} + \text{FP}) \times (\text{FP} + \text{TN})}$$

$$\bullet \text{ TSS} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} - \frac{\text{FP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

Due to less variation concerning data imbalance, since the Bobra & Couvidat's work [2] the TSS is considered the main metric to evaluate the performance of solar flares forecasting with classification problems. Previously, most authors used the HSS.

³ <https://pytorch.org/>: framework for training Deep Learning models with GPU support and automatic back-propagation.

⁴ <https://www.pytorchlightning.ai/>: Simplifies code by eliminating the need for an explicit loop.

⁵ <https://neptune.ai/>: Enables real-time metrics monitoring during model training. It also monitors hardware resources.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

At the end of the entire training process, we load the best model based on the epoch that presented the smallest error in the validation set (Valid Loss) to perform the test step. In the test step, we evaluate the test set, not seen by the models before. The Table 1 presents the results compared with Tang et al. [7]. We did not compare with Tang et al. [8] because they used a different dataset and made only the next 24h forecast.

Table 1. Performance comparison for solar flares forecasting of class $\geq M$ in the next 48h.

Model	PS [†] /NS [‡]	F1	ACC	POD	PRE	FAR	CSI	HSS	TSS
Tang et al.[7] - CNN [♠] ◊	3.95%	0.41	0.96	0.41	0.42	0.58	0.26	0.39	0.38
Tang et al.[7] - DNN [♠] ◊	3.95%	0.54	0.95	0.71	0.44	0.56	0.37	0.52	0.67
Tang et al.[7] - biLSTM [♠] ◊	3.95%	0.45	0.96	0.47	0.44	0.56	0.29	0.43	0.44
Tang et al.[7] - Fusion model [♠] ◊	3.95%	0.57	0.97	0.48	0.69	0.31	0.39	0.55	0.47
AlexNet [♠]	4.61%	0.50	0.97	0.34	0.93	0.07	0.33	0.49	0.34
ResNet-18 [♠]	4.61%	0.23	0.96	0.13	0.82	0.18	0.13	0.22	0.13
ResNet3D [♠]	4.61%	0.40	0.96	0.27	0.77	0.23	0.25	0.39	0.27
ResNetMC [♠]	4.61%	0.37	0.96	0.24	0.85	0.15	0.23	0.36	0.24
ResNet2D+1 [♠]	4.61%	0.56	0.97	0.49	0.66	0.34	0.39	0.54	0.48
Tang et al.[7] - F1_FFM [♠] ♡	4.75%	0.52	0.96	0.49	0.58	-	-	-	0.48
Tang et al.[7] - TSS_FFM [♠] ♡	4.75%	0.42	0.89	0.83	0.28	-	-	-	0.72

[†] Total of Positive Samples (1);

[‡] Total of Negative Samples (0);

[♠] Models optimized for F1 metric;

[♣] Models optimized for TSS metric;

◊ Values calculated according to the confusion matrix on Table 5 of Tang et al.[7].

♡ Fusion models tested with cross validation, according tables 7, 8 and 9 of Tang et al.[7]

Despite a small divergence in the number of samples between our test set and the Tang et al. [7] test set, the preliminary results shows that the CNNs2D, ResNet3D and ResNetMC did not perform very well (max TSS = 0.34) in relation of Tang et al. [7] models. However, the ResNet 2D+1 model achieved very similar results in all metrics (the biggest variation was +0.03 in FAR) compared to the preliminary Fusion model Tang et al. [7].

ResNet2D+1 also presented higher PRE for the definitive Fusion Models (_FFM) by Tang et al. [7] for solar flares forecasting of class $\geq M$ in the next 48h. It should be noted that the results from Tang et al. [7] _FFM in the last 2 lines of Table 1 were obtained with a different configuration of the test set through 5-fold crossvalidation.

Regarding Tang et al. [7] TSS-optimized (TSS_FFM), although it presents the best TSS (0.72), it also shows the worsts ACC (0.89) and PRE (0.28). Besides, Tang et al. [7] did not provide the confusion matrix or the FAR CSI and HSS metrics for the _FFM models, but we can infer that low PRE impacts these metrics.

CONCLUSIONS

The ResNet 2D+1 model achieved very similar results concerning the state of art models optimized for F1 metric for solar flares forecasting of class $\geq M$ in the next 48h. The ResNet 2D+1 model also presented metrics close to the definitive Fusion Model by Tang et al. [7] optimized for the F1 metric (F1_FFM). In future work, we intend to evaluate the performance of ResNet2D+1 optimized for the TSS metric.

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